

A Pulse Radiolysis Study of Aqueous Oxygenated Benzene in Presence of Nitrous Oxide.

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The reactions occurring during irradiation of aqueous benzene systems in presence of oxygen and nitrous oxide have been investigated by pulse radiolysis and gamma radiolysis. The formation and decay kinetics of the hydroxy cyclohexadienyl peroxy radical [$\text{PhH}(\text{OH})\text{O}_2^\bullet$] have been investigated in order to elucidate the mechanism of products formation in benzene radiolysis. Estimates of the molar extinction coefficients for the different radicals and their reaction rate constants have been made. It is concluded that the usually reported formation of muconic aldehyde type products are probably secondary products. The primary products from the peroxy radicals are probably unstable hydroperoxides which decompose further to the usually reported products, like phenol.

THE radiation chemistry of aqueous benzene in the presence and absence of oxygen has received much attention^{1,2} for the last two decades. Product yields and the mechanism of their formation have been widely discussed. Phenol, biphenyl, hydrogen peroxide, dihydroxy-benzenes and mucondialdehyde have been reported to be final products. The phenol yields do not agree between different authors mainly because of the non-specificity of the experimental techniques employed. The formation of aldehydes in presence of oxygen in aqueous benzene is explained² by a mechanism involving peroxy radicals which give rise to the hydroperoxides, which on elimination of water gives rise to the aldehyde.

Dorfman et al³ have investigated the pulse radiolysis of aqueous benzene in the presence and absence of oxygen and obtained the absorption spectra of hydroxy-cyclohexadienyl radical and the subsequent peroxy radical. It seems that in spite of much study the reactions in the radiolysis of aqueous benzene in the presence of oxygen are still not completely understood. One difficulty in all this work is to establish that the measured products are primary products and not due to subsequent reactions. These are very likely to occur in the gamma radiolysis since the primary products are much more reactive than benzene and irradiations must be carried out over relatively long times in order to obtain enough products for analysis. In order to minimise such effects in the present work, electron pulse irradiations of short duration have been used.

The main aim in the oxygenated systems was to test the possibility that the peroxy radical reaction suggested by Russell⁴ for aliphatic systems occurred with benzene also. From the pulse radiolysis work³ it seems probable that the following reactions occur in aqueous oxygenated system :

where PhH stands for benzene. Subsequent reactions of the peroxy radical are in doubt. One possibility is the elimination of water to give PhO_2^\bullet . It is difficult to see any obvious reaction of PhO_2^\bullet except hydrolysis to phenol and HO_2 , since the usual abstraction of H from benzene will be too endothermic. The reaction of Russell cannot be formulated since there is no H atom at the same carbon as peroxy group. However the reaction can be seen to occur with $\text{PhH}(\text{OH})\text{O}_2^\bullet$ radicals (ortho and para). The possible initial products would be catechol, hydroquinone, 1, 2 dihydroxy cyclohexadiene and 1, 4-dihydroxy cyclohexadiene, the latter two dehydrating to phenol. (One would expect to find 50% phenol, 25% catechol and 25% hydroquinone (assuming 1 : 1 ratio of ortho and para). However, it is necessary to establish that the kinetics required of such a scheme are observed and the present study was undertaken to throw light on these mechanisms under conditions where secondary reactions are kept to a minimum.

Experimental

Materials :

Benzene : B. D. H. Analar grade benzene was fractionally crystallised three times, each time rejecting 30% of the original volume. The fractionated benzene was dried over sodium and stored in dark in nitrogen atmosphere.

Water : Triply distilled water—first distillation in acid dichromate, second in acid permanganate and the last without any additive in quartz apparatus was used.

Hydroquinone : (QH_2). B. D. H. AnalaR grade hydroquinone was used as such.

Catechol : Reagent grade catechol was recrystallised from ethanol and used in the experiments.

Nitrous oxide and Oxygen : British Oxygen Co, nitrous oxide and oxygen were used as such without further purification.

Sample preparation and irradiation: Nitrous oxide and oxygen were allowed to mix at steady flow rates after passing through separate flow meters. The gaseous mixture was passed into triple distilled water after passing through liquid benzene for more than an hour. The concentration of nitrous oxide or oxygen was calculated from the partial pressure and the solubility of the particular gas in water at atmospheric pressure at room temperature. The concentrations of oxygen and nitrous oxide were varied by suitably changing their flow rates. The irradiation cell was made of fused silica with flat windows of 'supersil' with a 2.5 cm path length. A flow system using a remote controlled, motor operated three way stopcock was employed in filling and draining the cell after each irradiation. The irradiated liquid was forced out by argon and the cell was filled with a new batch of solution.

The pulse radiolysis was carried out at the Paterson Laboratories, Christie Hospital and Holt Radium Institute, Manchester using a 12 MeV linear electron accelerator. The pulse intensity was monitored by a secondary emission chamber. The optical system and electronic circuitry have been described elsewhere⁵. A modified Fricke dosimeter was used⁶ using $10^{-2} M$ ferrous sulphate in 0.8 N sulphuric acid saturated with oxygen in calibrating the secondary emission chamber to evaluate the absolute absorbed dose.

Kinetics and spectra of transient products: The oscilloscope trace at each wavelength was photographed with a 'Tektronix' C-13 camera on a polaroid film. The abscissa and ordinates of the oscilloscope trace represent the time and intensity of absorbed light respectively. From the coordinates of each point on the trace and a knowledge of the initial light intensity the optical densities at different times were calculated. The decay kinetics were examined for first or second order by follow up of the concentrations as a function of time.

Qualitative analysis for catechol: The presence of catechol in the sample was tested by a colorimetric method⁷ and by paper chromatographic method developed by Riley⁸. In the former a colored complex of resorcinol, catechol and iodine absorbing at 725 nm was developed at pH 5.7 (acetate buffer). Excess iodine is removed by thiosulphate. Acetone was added to the final solution before measuring the optical density at 725 nm against a reagent blank.

Analysis of hydroquinone and other oxidisable products: A quantitative method was developed for the analysis of reducing species in the irradiated medium at concentrations below about 5 μM . It depends on the reduction of ferric to ferrous and subsequent estimation of ferrous ion by the formation of the tris-*o*-Phenanthroline complex ion, $Fe(Phen)_3^{+2}$. A 0.1% solution of ortho phenanthroline was prepared in an acetate buffer (pH 5.7, 40 mM in acetate concentration). 4 ml of a freshly prepared ferric alum solution (~8 mM) was added to the test solution (= 20 ml) and then mixed with the *o*-phenanthroline solution (.0 ml). After about 5 min, 4 ml of a 50% ammonium fluoride solution was added

to complex the excess ferric ion. The optical density of the solution was monitored at 510 nm in a 10 cm cell using a reagent blank. A calibration graph, obtained by using hydroquinone as the reducing species, was employed in the analysis. It can be used to measure up to one μM of ferrous ion.

Ceric oxidation of hydroquinone: A sensitive test for hydroquinone is oxidation to benzoquinone which has a high absorption coefficient at 240 nm ($2.10 \times 10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) in ether. The oxidation was carried out by ceric sulphate in the presence of sulphuric acid.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of hydroxy cyclohexadienyl radical: In water saturated with benzene (~20 mM) and nitrous oxide. (~28 mM) the OH radical yield is $G_{OH} + G_{e^-} = 5.9$. The OH radicals add on to the benzene ring forming the PhH(OH) radical. Figure 1 gives the decay kinetics of the absorption at 310 nm due to this radical which is of second order indicating that PhH(OH) radical dimerises with itself rather than reacting with benzene. From the slopes of the second order decay plots for different absorbed doses, an average value for K/ϵ at 310 nm of $4.1 \times 10^5 cm sec^{-1}$ was obtained for this dimerisation reaction. The optical density immediately after the pulse gives a $G \epsilon$ value 2.05×10^4 . The total $G(OH)$ of 5.9 can be assumed to be equal to that of PhH(OH) because of the high concentration of benzene thus giving an extinction coefficient of $3.5 \times 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ for the PhH(OH) radical. From this value the rate constant for the dimerisation reaction

is calculated to be about $1.4 \times 10^9 M^{-1} sec^{-1}$.

Kinetics and spectra in presence of oxygen and nitrous oxide: When oxygen is present in the system along with nitrous oxide the following reactions take place:

The total OH concentration decreases in the presence of oxygen since part of the hydrated electrons are scavenged by oxygen in competition with nitrous oxide. The dimerisation of PhH(OH) radical can be suppressed by working at low concentrations of this radical by using low doses, and oxygen concentration much in excess of the radical concentration.

Fig. 1

Figure 1 : a. Second order decay of 310 nm absorption in the pulse radiolysis of N_2O saturated aqueous benzene; (0.2 μ . sec. pulse, 0.5 K. rad);
 b. —do— (1.0 μ . sec. pulse, 2.66 K. rads).

Fig 2

Figure 2 : a. End of pulse spectrum in pulse radiolysis of aqueous benzene + $N_2O + O_2$;
 b. Absorption spectrum after initial fast decay in the pulse radiolysis of aqueous benzene with nitrous oxide (25 mM) and oxygen (80 μ . M.)

Figure 2a gives the absorption spectrum obtained immediately after a 0.2 μ sec. pulse in water saturated with benzene containing 80 μ M of oxygen and 25 mM of nitrous oxide. This oxygen concentration was used so that the reaction of PhH (OH) radical with oxygen can be seen on the oscilloscope on a suitable time scale. The spectrum shows a broad absorption band between 260 nm and 320 nm with a peak around 310 nm and is identical with the one obtained in the absence of oxygen attributed to PhH (OH) radical. However, the decay kinetics of this species is now first order showing its reaction with oxygen. The spectrum of the product of this reaction is given in Figure 2b which agrees with that attributed for the peroxy radical PhH (OH) O_2^{\cdot} . This spectrum is broader than the one due to the PhH (OH) radical and has two absorption maxima, one around 275 nm and the other around 310 nm.

The first order decay constant was determined to be $(4 \pm .3) \times 10^8 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for the PhH (OH) radical at an oxygen concentration of 1.04 mM and nitrous oxide concentration of 4.5 mM. This value remained constant over a three fold dose range. From this oxygen concentration the rate constant k_2 was calculated to be $3.9 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. This value compares well with $(5 \pm .6) \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ obtained by Dorfman et al³ for the same reaction.

The subsequent decay of PhH(OH) O_2^{\cdot} radical is found to be second order with a k/ϵ value of $(1.35 \pm .15) \times 10^6 \text{ cm sec}^{-1}$ at 310 nm. The $G \epsilon$ value for this radical was found to be 3.1×10^3 at the same wavelength and oxygen concentration of 1.04 mM and nitrous oxide concentration of 4.5 mM. At these concentrations of nitrous oxide and oxygen the value for $G\text{-PhH (OH)}$ is calculated to be 4.5 from the known values of k_4 and k_5 and assuming all the OH radicals are converted into PhH(OH) at the high benzene concentration ($\sim 20\text{mM}$). From a knowledge of the rate constants for PhH (OH) radical dimerisation (k_3) and its rate constant for reaction with oxygen (k_2) it is found that 95% of the hydroxy cyclohexadienyl radicals react with oxygen at this concentration of oxygen to give the peroxy radical. Thus it can be assumed that the G value of PhH (OH) is almost equal to that of PhH (OH) O_2^{\cdot} radical being equal to 4.5 as calculated above. From this value and the $G \epsilon$ value at 310 nm the molar extinction coefficient of the peroxy radical at 310 nm is calculated to be $(690 \pm 100) \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Using this value the rate constant for the reaction

k_6 was calculated to be $(9.3 \pm 1.2) \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

Products spectra of the peroxy radical reaction :
 The rate constant k_7 shows that with a pulse dose of 2.9 K rads in the presence of 1.04 mM oxygen and 4.5 mM of nitrous oxide all the peroxy radical has disappeared in about one millisecond. Figures 3a and 3b give the absorption spectra of the products of this peroxy radical reaction, 4 m. sec. and 25 sec. after the pulse. The same spectrum is present after one second

and 50 sec. The spectra could be obtained only above 260 nm as benzene absorbs strongly below this wavelength. A small correction needs to be applied (less than 5%) to the optical densities at 260 nm and 270 nm for the increased transmission due to the removal of benzene.

The spectrum after 4 m. sec. shows a pronounced maximum between 270 nm and 275 nm with a shoulder around 290 nm. There is very little absorption above 300 nm. At one second after this, the maximum is no longer present. There is relatively a large increase in absorption below 270 nm and a smaller increase in longer wavelengths where there now appears an absorption tail extending to 320 nm. There seems to be only minor changes over the next 50 seconds.

tion of the products, the neutral solution giving the spectrum of the ionised forms.

Previous reports⁹ have proposed muconic aldehyde type products to be present in the irradiated solutions. The freshly gamma irradiated solution is reported to show strong absorption maxima at 368 nm and 345 nm which are attributed to phenol and β -hydroxy mucondialdehyde (β -HMD). Earlier workers have suggested mucondialdehyde¹. To give an idea of the absorptions of the suggested products, viz., mucondialdehyde, α -hydroxy muconic semialdehyde, β -HMD, phenol, catechol and hydroquinone, spectra of these are given in Figures 4a and 4b.

Fig 3

- Figure 3 : Absorption spectra of products after different times in the p.r. of aq. benzene + O₂ (1.04 mM) and nitrous oxide (4.5 mM)
- 0.4 m. sec. after pulse ;
 - x 25 sec.
 - . 2 hrs. after pulse (in acid, benzene removed).

In order to extend the absorption spectra below 260 nm the benzene must be removed. This was done by passing argon through the pulse irradiated sample for one hour after having made the solution 12 mM in sulphuric acid to prevent any oxidation of the primary products. The spectrum obtained is shown in Figure 3c. It will be seen that the maximum is at a lower wavelength compared to the spectrum after one second and there is appreciable absorption at 240 nm. These changes may be associated with a change in the ionisa-

tion of the products, the neutral solution giving the spectrum of the ionised forms. It is clear that the spectra of the present products differ considerably from that of Balakrishnan and Reddy⁹ attributed to β -HMD and if the spectrum given is correct, one can say that no such compound is formed in our conditions. Also α -hydroxy muconic semialdehyde can be ruled out for the same reason, viz., it has a large absorption at 350 nm. From the spectrum of mucondialdehyde it will be seen that the observed absorption may have some contribution from this compound. However, it cannot account for the large absorptions at

Figure 4 : a. Absorption Spectra of :
 O Mucondialdehyde¹¹; x α -hydroxy muconic-semialdehyde¹² ;
 . β -hydroxy mucondialdehyde⁹.
 b. Absorption spectra of
 O phenol ; x catechol ; . hydroquinone.

Figure 5 : O Absorption spectrum at 4 m. sec. after pulse ;
 x Theoretical spectrum assuming only phenol and catechol to be present.

the lower wavelengths and hence, if it is present other compounds must also be present. Turning now to compare the product spectra with those of phenol, catechol and quinol, we see that the 4 m. sec. spectrum is similar to a combination of phenol and catechol. However, when composite spectrum consisting of only these two is made up by calculating the fraction of each from the absorption at two wavelengths (Figure 5) it will be seen that it is not possible to match the spectra at the lower wavelength end. The products have more absorption beyond 290 nm and less at 275 nm. The former might be thought to be due to quinol since it has a big absorption at 290 nm and beyond. However, the observed spectrum falls off too quickly at 290 nm to 300 nm to be accounted for in this way. Further Riley's method gave a negative test for catechol, thus indicating its absence in any measurable extent. The product spectra in acid after removal of benzene (Figure 5) shows larger absorption from 260 nm downwards than can be accommodated for by the hydroxy benzenes alone.

Ether extraction spectra: Previous workers^{2,10} employed ether extraction to concentrate the products

and since the spectrum closely resembled that of phenol it was used to calculate G (Phenol). This extraction procedure was repeated with a solution of benzene containing 1.04 mM oxygen and 4.5 mM of nitrous oxide which had been irradiated with a single electron pulse. After removing benzene with argon the ether extract was made either 12 mM in sulphuric acid, or neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. The spectra of the ether solutions are given in Figures 6a and 6b. Figure 7 gives the spectrum of the residual aqueous solution. As will be seen by comparison with the phenol spectrum neither of these can be said to be identical. Both are much broader and although phenol may be present other material is there as well.

To test whether there is hydroquinone present in the acid ether extract, it was shaken with dilute ceric sulphate and the spectrum was obtained again. In a blank experiment with an ether solution of QH₂, the latter was quantitatively oxidised to quinone as shown by a large increase in absorption at 240 nm. However, although the absorption of the ether extract at 240 nm was increased by about two times by ceric sulphate, this increase corresponds to only a small

Fig. 6

Figure 6: Absorption spectra of ether extract (1.8 K. rads)
 a. O Extract from acid medium;
 b. x Extract from solution neutralised with bicarbonate (both solutions 3.7 times more concentrated than the original).

amount of QH_2 ($G=0.37$), assuming all the increased absorption at 240 nm is due to *p*-benzoquinone only.

In order to test the total reducing power of the irradiated solution, the solution was allowed to reduce ferric ion in presence of *o*-phenanthroline giving rise to ferroin which was estimated by its absorption at 510 nm. The *G* values of the reducing product (in hydroquinone equivalents) is given in Table 1. It is seen that this yield is much in excess of the QH_2 estimated above. This indicates that there are other products present in the solution having reducing properties.

TABLE—1. YIELDS OF REDUCING PRODUCTS IN THE PULSE OR GAMMA RADIOLYSIS OF NEUTRAL AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF BENZENE

System	Dose absorbed K. rads	G(reducing products) QH_2 equivalents
1.04 mM O_2 , 4.5 mM N_2O , single electron pulse	1.8	1.3
—do—	3.2	1.02
—do—	5.2	1.7
—do—	6.0	1.5
1.04 mM O_2 , 4.5 mM N_2O Co^{60} gamma radiolysis	3.0	0.24

Fig. 7

Figure 7: Absorption spectra of products not extractable in ether, in aqueous solution; ether removed;
 O acid medium; original acid solution before extraction;
 x neutral medium; . original bicarbonate solution.

It will be seen that except at 240 nm and 230 nm where the absorption is small and possibly inaccurate, absorption of the acid solution is decreased as a result of ether extraction. However in the bicarbonate medium, although the prominent peak has been removed there is considerable absorption left (Figure 7), which below 260 nm is actually greater than was present originally. This strongly suggests that there has been a chemical reaction as a result of adding the bicarbonate which produces ionic species not extractable in ether.

Gamma irradiation experiments: The above observations suggest that in earlier gamma radiation studies where appreciable absorptions at wavelengths greater than 300 nm have been observed, the absorptions are due to secondary products arising from the large doses used. Perhaps these may also be due to the products resulting from hydrated electrons or hydrogen atoms and not only due to OH radicals.

To confirm this, gamma irradiations were carried out with low doses in the oxygen-nitrous oxide mixtures. The absorption spectra of the products after removal of benzene are shown in Figures 8a and 8b

for two cases of 3 and 6.2 K. rads of absorbed doses. It is seen that in the first place the optical densities at all wavelengths are in the ratio of the gamma doses which shows that no secondary products are present. Furthermore, the large absorption at 350 nm reported frequently is not present suggesting that this is indeed a secondary product.

Fig. 8

Figure 8 : Absorption spectra of products formed in the Co^{60} gamma radiolysis of aqueous benzene containing oxygen (1.04 mM) and nitrous oxide (4.5 mM) :

- 0.3 K. rads of absorbed dose ;
- x 6.2 K rads.

Possible reactions : It is clear that the products of the peroxy radical in this system do not correspond to those expected on the Russell mechanism¹. Hydroquinone is present in only small amounts and there is no evidence for catechol. It has been found that the reaction is second order in peroxy radicals and a possible alternative is probably as follows (see structure). This suggests the production of hydroperoxy benzene and hydroperoxy phenol. It is possible that these compounds decompose slowly by hydrolysis to give benzene, phenol and hydrogen peroxide. Such a slow formation of phenol has indeed been reported by Dorfman et. al.³ but their

method of estimation is open to criticism. Alternative decomposition by O-O fission is also possible and will lead to complex hydroxylated products, some of which might account for the observation at high doses where long times are involved.

Conclusion

The peroxy radicals produced in the radiolysis of aqueous benzene react together to give products which are not those previously reported to be found in gamma radiolysis. The nature of these products could not be established, but neither are they those which should be given by Russell mechanism for peroxy radical—peroxy radical reaction. It seems probable that labile peroxides are first produced which could lead by thermal decomposition and/or hydrolysis to the commonly detected products.

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